

NIGERIA'S BUSINESS SECTORS AND CRUCIAL RESOURCES FOR ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: Finance has often been featured as one of the most crucial resources needed to promote entrepreneurial activities, but the question is whether this assertion holds true in every business sector. This paper, therefore, examines some resources that promote entrepreneurial activities across designated business sectors in Nigeria. Specifically, it identified the most crucial resources in every sector of the economy. It is anticipated that by examining some resource factors across business sectors, resources that enhance entrepreneurial activities will be industry-specific and different. Stratified random sampling was used to ensure adequate representation in each sector, and 650 questionnaires were administered in Lagos, one of Nigeria's metropolitan cities and economic hubs. Descriptive and Inferential Statistics were used to analyze the obtained data. The descriptive statistics show the frequency of resources enhancing entrepreneurial activities in each sector, while Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is used to pinpoint the most crucial resource factor in each sector. The research findings confirmed variations in the level of importance across the selected business sectors. Some resources are more crucial than others, and finance was not the most crucial resource factor in the selected business sectors in Nigeria. The authors therefore propose several extension of this study.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Activities, Resources, Business Sectors, Nigeria.

Introduction

Diverse studies have iterated numerous resources needed for entrepreneurial growth and development. These resources are oftentimes referred to as either sustainability or key success factors that are likened to basic nutrients needed for human growth and development (Abdelwahed, Soomro & Shah, 2022; Tur-Porcar, Roig-Tierno & Llorca Mestre, 2018; Akinyemi, 2016). Multiple studies emphasize some resources for specific businesses, while some authors unpacked the various sustainability factors for entrepreneurship growth and examined them from one business phase to another (Akinyemi and Ojah, 2018; Akinyemi, 2016). However, there is the dearth of studies on the relative importance of each of these factors in every sector of an economy. Hence, there is a need to move from universal views and examine some already identified resources across some selected business sectors.

Resources such as raw materials, management skills, personality traits, good customer services, technology, and finance have been identified as necessary for business growth and sustenance (Abdelwahed, Soomro & Shah, 2022; Akinyemi & Ojah, 2018; Tur-Porcar, Roig-Tierno & Llorca Mestre, 2018; Akinyemi & Adejumo, 2017). These diverse resources are often given diverse nomenclature but have similar denominators when examined closely. For instance, management skills and good customer services are roles performed by an organization's workforce, otherwise called labor. Plants, machines, and equipment differ from one business sector to another but can be denominated as technology. Similarly, the raw materials needed for the production of goods and services differ from one entrepreneurial activity or business sector to another but are all uniformly referred to as raw materials, just as the funding portfolio or combination of funds needed may vary from one sector to another but are all referred to as finance. For uniformity, clarity, and easy clarification across business sectors, therefore, this study identifies and stratifies these resources as four namely; raw materials, finance, technology, and labor (Tur-Porcar, Roig-Tierno & Llorca Mestre, 2018; Akinyemi, 2016).

For sector classification, entrepreneurial activities within an economy are occasionally categorized into three, five, or seven business sectors. The three-sector theory on business classification comprises prime/primary, ancillary/secondary and tertiary sectors (Jegade, *et al.* 2019; Chete *et al.*, 2014). The five-sector theory describes business activities as consisting of prime/primary, ancillary/secondary, quaternary, tertiary and quinary activities. However, the seven-sector classification gives an elaborate description and makes comparison across entrepreneurial activities easier. Hence, this study examines the four most featured resources for entrepreneurial activities across seven selected business sectors in Nigeria.

Empirical and Theoretical Review

Entrepreneurship has been undeniably identified as a pivotal catalyst for economic advancement in multiple nations. It is often defined as problem-solving and risk-taking endeavors (Prince, Chapman & Cassey, 2021), and they are observed to be conducted by unique individuals having uncommon skills and abilities to combine relevant resources in order to achieve great feats (Ratten, 2023; Gartner, 1990). These relevant resources are deemed crucial and often determine the altitude, growth, and sustainability of every entrepreneurial venture (Ozturk, 2021; Celtekliligil, 2020).

A couple of theoretical views, such as resource dependence theory (Ozturk, 2021; Celtekliligil, 2020), population ecology theory (Lomnicki, 2018; Hannan & Freeman, 1977), and evolutionary standpoints have iterated the importance of resource obtainability for effective business operations and entrepreneurial progress. In essence, resource paucity establishes an impartial restraint on entrepreneurial activities and outcomes. Resource dependence theory rationalizes how entrepreneurs can use requisite resources from the immediate and other environments to foster their businesses. The theory emphasizes that environments play vital roles in shaping the existence and progression of business undertakings. The theory stresses that entrepreneurs and business entities engage in transactional interactions with their environments because they cannot autonomously generate all the resources needed for production.

Although these theories have undeniably boosted further insights into the entrepreneurial process by conveying the resource side of entrepreneurship, the ecological angle contests the intellectual conjecture that business development and feat depend exclusively on entrepreneurial attributes. At one angle, ecology theory flags

resources, and at the other, cognitive theory flags entrepreneurs' traits, and the convergence is that both factors are essential for entrepreneurial buoyancy.

Resource-based entrepreneurship theories maintain that access to resources such as raw materials, finance, technology, and labor is an important predictor of business growth (Ozturk, 2021; Celtekligil, 2020). For example, for technology-based resources, the use of internet facilities and other digital resources enables entrepreneurs to achieve more mutual engagements with other business vendors and advance their proficiency in handling inter-firm contacts. Therefore, they extend their client base and achieve global competitiveness (Usman *et al.*, 2024; Mbukanma & Goswami, 2023).

For finance-based resources, access to loans and mortgages boosts business expansions and ensures stability. Finance is considered to be an essential requirement at both the start-up phase and continuity stages of businesses (Yadav, Venkata & Pradhan, 2018; Anwar, Tajeddini & Ullah, 2020). Many lucrative ventures and novel ideas have reportedly died prematurely due to the unavailability of funds for kick-off and expansion. These and other resources are essential for the growth and sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures. However, their relative importance in each business sector must be determined.

Thus, it is imperative to fathom how inversely these resources relate to different sectors of the economy. The foremost motivation is to determine whether these resources are uniformly essential in every business sector. In order to achieve this, the first step is to examine the resources often needed in each sector, the second step is to establish the most vital resources in each sector, and third, to compare the outcomes across the selected sectors.

Nigeria is one of Africa's emerging economies and is esteemed to be of very high economic relevance, both continentally and across the globe (Wright & Okolo, 2018; Ogunnubi & Okeke-Uzodike, 2016). Diverse kinds of entrepreneurial activities exist in Nigeria, ranging from tangible products and services such as clothes and footwear, food and beverages, books and coals, and medical and hospitality services to list but a few. Financial institutions in Nigeria usually place high demands on entrepreneurs in terms of collaterals funding requirements. Hence, most entrepreneurs and business owners resort to informal funding sources. Entrepreneurial activities in each of these business lines require a good combination of the four identified resources—raw materials, finance, technology, and labor—to thrive well. Entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria's major lines of businesses and their classification into seven major sectors are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Major lines of business in Nigeria

No.	Sector	Description
1	Pharmaceuticals	Manufacture and transactions of chemicals, drugs, rubber products, and insecticides
2	Food	Sales, production, and processing of farm produce, food items, beverages and drinks.
3	Service	Service rendering organizations such as banks, medical doctors, architects, nurses, plumbers, auto mechanics, hairdressers, and engineers.
4	Textile	Manufacturing of fabrics, drapes, clothes and apparel
5	Wood	Wooden items, paper, and wood products like coal

6	Telecommunication	Manufacture and sales of mobile phones, earpods, computers, power banks, electrical appliances and electronics.
7	Metal	Production and sale of roofing sheets, metals, cutlery, and other steel or iron products.

Source: Adapted from Akinyemi, 2016 (Pg 86)

Therefore, the proposed hypothesis is as follows:

Hypothesis: every resource is equally critical in all selected business sectors.

3.0 Research Methodology

A total of 650 questionnaires were randomly and purposively administered among entrepreneurs in Lagos, Nigeria’s most popular metropolitan city, to ensure adequate representation of every business sector. The respondents were certified entrepreneurs between 18-64 years who were single proprietors or co-owners of surviving businesses. They were first asked to identify crucial resources that would help them improve their personal experiences while running their businesses.

The chi-square test revealed the association between the identified variables, whereas Cronbach’s Alpha showed the reliability and internal consistency of the variables. Descriptive statistics reflected the resources adopted in each business sector, while Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was adopted to identify the most crucial sustainability factor(s) in each sector (Kherif & Latypova, 2020; Shlens, 2014).

4.0 Research Results and Discussion of Findings

Background Information on Entrepreneurs and Business Sectors

Table 2 presents the backdrop information on Nigerian entrepreneurs and the seven major classifications of entrepreneurial activities in the country. The three most populous sectors are the service, food, and textile sectors, respectively (Figure 1). Nigeria’s service sector (30%) comprises businesses such as medical practitioners, children’s daycare centers, and hairdressing salons. Restaurant owners, raw food and fruit sellers dominated Nigeria’s food sector (17%), while textile businesses (13%) comprised cloth manufacturers, cloth vendors and dressmakers.

Regarding gender and business ownership, 63% of the sampled entrepreneurs in Nigeria were male, and their median age were 31 years. The age distribution inclined favorably toward the youthful age range of 18-33 years and represents moderately more than half, that is, 53%, of Nigeria’s sampled entrepreneurs. About 27% were between 34 and 41 years old, and only around 6% (4%+2.2%) were aged 50 years and above.

Table 2: Distribution by Information on Business Sectors

VARIABLES	NIGERIA	
	FREQUENCY N=609	Percentage
Gender		
Male	385	63.2
Female	224	36.8
Age in Years		
18-24	80	13.3
25-33	238	39.6

34-41	159	26.5
42-49	87	14.5
50-57	24	4.0
58-65	13	2.2
Median Age	31.2 years	
Business Sectors		
Food	104	17.4
Textile	77	12.9
Wood	43	7.2
Pharmaceuticals	43	7.2
Metal	75	12.5
Telecommunication	74	12.4
Service	182	30.4

Source: Authors' field work.

Figure 1: Pie Chart Representation of each Sector
Reliability Coefficients and Factor Loadings of Resources

Table 3 presents a holistic view of the reliability estimates, internal structure, and variance of the resources in Nigeria, while Table 5 presents the same results across the selected business sectors. The crux of the findings is that the resources across all business sectors do not carry equal weight. Some resources are more important than others. In table 3 for instance, technology recorded the strongest effect wholistically but varied across the nominated business sectors in Table 5. Hence, upcoming entrepreneurs and pertinent stakeholders in Nigeria should be aware of the variations among these examined resources as they exert varied impacts on entrepreneurial activities.

Table 3: Internal Structure and Domain of Resources in Nigeria

	Factor loading	Alpha/ Variance
Resources	4 items	
Finance	0.6	
Raw Materials	0.7	0.82
Technology	0.9	79.2
Labor	0.8	

Source: Authors' field work.

Table 4 displays the bivariate distribution of resources, highlighting both the statistical significance and distribution pattern of each variable within the domain. As reflected in Table 4, without controlling for business sectors, all variables were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that the collective measure of the examined resources aligns with existing literature (Ozturk, 2021; Celtekliligil, 2020; Anwar, Tajeddini & Ullah, 2020; Yadav, Venkata & Pradhan, 2018) in which several resources were reported as vital for entrepreneurial progress. The prior studies, which flaunt the significance of these resources, were piloted independently at diverse points in time and did not specific the sectors or stages where these resources are most vital. Hence, without adjusting for business sectors, the holistic view is that all resources are equally significant. However, when control variables, such as sectors, are introduced, variations exist, as shown in Table 6.

Figure 2 also highlights the frequency of crucial resources based on respondents' perception before they were asked to rank the resources based on their personal experiences.

Table 4: Cross-Tabulation of Resources in Nigeria

Nigeria	(n=598)	
	Percentage/p-value	Chi-square
Resources	4 items	
Finance	69.1 (0.00*)	55.52
Raw Materials	17.6 (0.00*)	53.94
Technology	18.2 (0.00*)	53.64
Labor	23.4 (0.00*)	53.82

Source: Authors' field work.

Note: * significant at $p < .05$

The Most Crucial Resources Adopted by Each Business Sector

After confirming that the resources are not evenly vital in all the identified business sectors, the next step was to assess their comparative importance and, lastly, to identify the most crucial in each business sector. Principal Component Analysis was expended to identify the most crucial resource factor(s) in each business sector. Table 7 presents the Eigenvalues of the diverse combinations of resources adopted by entrepreneurs in each business sector. The results show that finance is the most vital sector, except the service sector in Nigeria. That is, the most vital resource needed for entrepreneurial activities is not the same across all sectors. Consequently, prospective entrepreneurs and investors seeking to establish businesses in these sectors must take cognizance of their peculiarities in order to avoid disappointment and harness the maximum returns.

Table 5: Internal Structure and Domain of Resource Factors in Nigeria’s Selected Business Sectors

Sectors	Food		Textile		Wood		Pharmaceutical		Metal		Telecommunication		Services	
	Factor loading	Alpha / variance	Factor loading	Alpha/ Variance	Factor loading	Alpha / variance	Factor loading	Alpha/ variance	Factor loading	Alpha / variance	Factor loading	Alpha / variance	Factor loading	Alpha / variance
Resources	4 items													
Finance	0.7		0.6		0.8		0.8		0.8		0.6		-	
Raw Materials	0.7	0.74	0.6	0.62	0.9	0.67	-	0.84	0.8	0.79	0.7	0.74	0.7	0.83
Technology	0.5	82.3	0.7	82.8	0.9	80.6	-	85.4	0.9	78.2	0.8	82.0	0.7	82.2
Labor	0.7		0.6		0.8		0.8		0.8		0.7		0.6	

Note: Factor loadings are depicted only if 0.5 or more in the sub-scales. Internal consistency was measured using Cronbach’s alpha and explained variance as presented in the same column.

Table 6: Cross-Tabulation of Nigeria’s Business Sectors and Crucial Resources for Entrepreneurial Activities

Sectors	Food (n=104)		Textile (n=77)		Wood (n=43)		Pharmaceutical (n=43)		Metal (n=75)		Telecommunication (n=74)		Services (n=182)	
	Percent/ p-value	Chi-square	Percent / p-value	Chi-square	Percent / p-value	Chi-square	Percent/ p-value	Chi-square	Percent/ p-value	Chi-square	Percent/ p-value	Chi-square	Percent / p-value	Chi-square
Resources	4 items													
Finance	70.2 (0.20)	3.18	72.7 (0.72)	0.66	72.1 (0.89)	0.21	69.8 (0.56)	1.19	69.3 (0.79)	0.46	66.2 (0.86)	0.29	67.0 (0.79)	0.47
Raw Materials	24.0 (0.04*)	6.33	16.9 (0.98)	0.03	25.6 (0.36)	2.05	11.6 (0.29)	2.48	16.0 (0.73)	0.64	5.4 (0.01*)	8.61	19.2 (0.74)	0.62
Technology	9.6 (0.01*)	9.92	9.1 (0.09)	4.80	23.3 (0.66)	0.84	18.6 (0.56)	1.17	22.7 (0.46)	1.58	32.4 (0.00*)	11.91	18.1 (0.96)	0.09
Labor	27.9 (0.11)	4.39	25.9 (0.81)	0.41	16.3 (0.53)	1.25	16.3 (0.27)	2.63	26.7 (0.62)	0.96	14.9 (0.20)	3.25	25.3 (0.67)	0.79

Note: * significant at $p < .05$

Table 7: Principal Component Analysis of Resources Factors in Nigeria’s Selected Business Sectors

Business Sectors	Food	Textile	Wood	Pharmaceutical	Metal	Telecommunication	Services
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	Factor 1	KM O	Factor 1	KMO	Factor 1	KM O								
Resources	4 items													
Finance	0.702 ♦	51.1	0.729 ♦		0.698 ♦		0.707 ♦		0.690 ♦		0.704 ♦		0.587	
Raw Materials	0.609		0.471	49.8	0.533	51.5	0.545	51.5	0.572	51.6	0.552	52.8	0.690♦	52.5
Technology	0.219		0.176		0.260		0.215		0.295		0.139		0.426	
Labor	0.519		0.625		0.598		0.610		0.562		0.624		0.472	

Note: The most crucial factors are indicated in bold with “♦” sign

Source: Authors’ field work.

Figure 2: Bar Chart Representation of Crucial Resource Factors in Each Sector

Conclusion

Finance has often been featured as a vital resource needed for entrepreneurial activities, but there is a dearth of details on the specifics across business sectors. Raw materials, labor and technology have also featured as vital resources for entrepreneurial activities, but their relative importance in each business sector need more exploration. The findings from this study suggest that some resources are more vital than others across designated business sectors in Nigeria. Hence, variations exist in the most crucial resources that enhance entrepreneurial activities across business sectors within an economy.

The caveat, therefore, is to disabuse people’s minds from the general notion that finance is the most crucial resource at all times. The authors opine that some fascinating insights may be innate in studies that examine these resources across different geographic locations of a particular economy, and thereby propose several extensions of this study.

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